

Supplementary Figure 1

Bivalves

Supplementary Figure 2

Gastropods

Supplementary Figure 3

Total assemblage

Panzano

Supplementary Figure 4

Total assemblage

Po 3

Supplementary Figure 5

Total assemblage

Po 4

Supplementary Figure 6

Total assemblage

Bivalves

Gastropods

NA
(not enough samples,
see figure S3 and / or table S3)

Supplementary Figure 7

Bivalves

Panzano

Supplementary Figure 8

Bivalves

Po 3

Supplementary Figure 9

Bivalves

Po 4

Supplementary Figure 10

Gastropods

Panzano

Supplementary Figure 11

Gastropods

Po 4

Supplementary Figure 12

Percentage predators

Supplementary Figure 13

Supplementary Figure 14

Supplementary Figure 15

Supplementary table 1

Station	Core number	Water depth	Coordinates		Location	Core length	Core diameter
			Latitude	Longitude			
Po3	M13	21 m	44.8425°N	12.5379°E	west of the Po di Tolle lobe	152 cm	16 cm
	M14	21 m	44.842117°N	12.538867°E	west of the Po di Tolle lobe	152 cm	16 cm
Po4	M20	21 m	44.731433°N	12.440333°E	southeast of the Goro-Gnocca lobe	152 cm	16 cm
	M21	21 m	44.730683°N	12.4401°E	southeast of the Goro-Gnocca lobe	155 cm	16 cm
Panzano	M28	12 m	45.735467°N	13.600533°E	northern Gulf of Trieste	150 cm	16 cm
	M29	12 m	45.735367°N	13.600483°E	northern Gulf of Trieste	150 cm	16 cm

Supplementary table 2

Station	Region	Core depth (cm)	Time bin	All mollusks		Bivalves		Gastropods		Scaphopods		<i>Varicorbula gibba</i>		<i>Kurtiella bidentata</i>		<i>Turritellina tricarinata</i>		<i>Tritia varicosa</i>	
				N	DF	N	DF	N	DF	N	DF	N	DF	N	DF	N	DF	N	DF
Panzano	Isonzo	0-4	late 20th to early 21st c.	368	0,15	243	0,19	113	0,07	12	0	82	0,27	16	0,5	10	0,5	43	0,05
Panzano	Isonzo	4-8	late 20th to early 21st c.	447	0,19	263	0,26	174	0,1	10	0	107	0,36	27	0,56	9	0,56	92	0,04
Panzano	Isonzo	8-12	late 20th to early 21st c.	351	0,2	218	0,27	116	0,09	17	0,06	94	0,28	39	0,49	8	0,38	74	0,08
Panzano	Isonzo	12-16	late 20th to early 21st c.	586	0,28	361	0,35	196	0,17	29	0,03	119	0,38	96	0,63	36	0,53	105	0,09
Panzano	Isonzo	16-20	late 19th to early 20th c.	555	0,26	316	0,31	209	0,22	30	0	74	0,35	120	0,45	54	0,65	83	0,07
Panzano	Isonzo	20-25	late 19th to early 20th c.	513	0,24	332	0,28	157	0,21	24	0	57	0,21	155	0,45	56	0,45	44	0,05
Panzano	Isonzo	25-30	late 19th to early 20th c.	597	0,33	410	0,34	169	0,33	18	0	79	0,37	179	0,49	77	0,56	34	0,18
Panzano	Isonzo	30-35	late 19th to early 20th c.	445	0,3	296	0,35	131	0,23	18	0	65	0,46	118	0,48	47	0,53	37	0,08
Panzano	Isonzo	35-40	late 19th to early 20th c.	512	0,24	328	0,23	164	0,27	20	0	85	0,26	106	0,43	58	0,59	35	0,11
Panzano	Isonzo	40-45	late 19th to early 20th c.	533	0,24	367	0,23	151	0,29	15	0	132	0,22	107	0,38	60	0,63	41	0,07
Panzano	Isonzo	45-50	17th to early 19th c.	405	0,23	285	0,24	114	0,23	6	0	66	0,27	81	0,44	38	0,58	17	0,06
Panzano	Isonzo	50-55	17th to early 19th c.	309	0,23	210	0,23	92	0,25	7	0	41	0,54	72	0,31	35	0,51	9	0
Panzano	Isonzo	55-60	17th to early 19th c.	239	0,24	163	0,23	72	0,28	4	0	29	0,28	68	0,31	29	0,55	13	0,15
Panzano	Isonzo	60-65	17th to early 19th c.	230	0,2	159	0,2	68	0,21	3	0	39	0,36	56	0,23	25	0,48	5	0
Panzano	Isonzo	65-70	17th to early 19th c.	154	0,27	116	0,28	35	0,26	3	0	34	0,62	37	0,24	15	0,47	5	0
Panzano	Isonzo	70-75	17th to early 19th c.	150	0,2	121	0,21	28	0,14	1	0	24	0,29	41	0,29	9	0,11	6	0,17
Panzano	Isonzo	75-80	17th to early 19th c.	139	0,2	105	0,23	33	0,12	1	0	26	0,38	36	0,28	10	0,4	4	0
Panzano	Isonzo	80-85	17th to early 19th c.	125	0,22	89	0,27	33	0,09	3	0	9	0,22	30	0,5	11	0,27	7	0
Panzano	Isonzo	85-90	17th to early 19th c.	211	0,27	156	0,28	47	0,3	8	0	19	0,26	52	0,44	22	0,59	5	0
Panzano	Isonzo	90-95	17th to early 19th c.	247	0,22	163	0,21	77	0,27	7	0	23	0,57	45	0,4	38	0,5	4	0
Panzano	Isonzo	95-100	17th to early 19th c.	231	0,25	170	0,24	55	0,29	6	0	34	0,47	48	0,29	34	0,47	4	0
Panzano	Isonzo	100-105	17th to early 19th c.	322	0,26	209	0,23	111	0,32	2	0	60	0,37	45	0,2	63	0,54	11	0
Panzano	Isonzo	105-110	17th to early 19th c.	271	0,27	187	0,23	83	0,36	1	0	45	0,36	44	0,39	42	0,67	3	0,33
Panzano	Isonzo	110-115	17th to early 19th c.	191	0,4	117	0,31	74	0,54	0	0	39	0,49	24	0,42	50	0,78	4	0
Panzano	Isonzo	115-120	17th to early 19th c.	209	0,38	116	0,31	90	0,49	3	0	40	0,5	31	0,42	64	0,67	3	0
Panzano	Isonzo	120-125	17th to early 19th c.	188	0,29	136	0,22	49	0,51	3	0	42	0,43	24	0,33	27	0,81	3	0
Panzano	Isonzo	125-130	17th to early 19th c.	150	0,27	103	0,21	40	0,48	7	0	41	0,32	18	0,28	26	0,69	1	0
Panzano	Isonzo	130-135	17th to early 19th c.	263	0,21	178	0,16	81	0,32	4	0,25	70	0,29	28	0,18	56	0,41	3	0
Panzano	Isonzo	135-140	17th to early 19th c.	312	0,22	195	0,18	98	0,35	19	0	47	0,32	53	0,3	60	0,55	6	0
Panzano	Isonzo	140-145	17th to early 19th c.	210	0,26	129	0,27	70	0,29	11	0	26	0,31	45	0,47	34	0,47	4	0,25
Panzano	Isonzo	145-150	17th to early 19th c.	208	0,22	140	0,18	61	0,31	7	0,14	31	0,19	36	0,28	32	0,53	5	0
Po 3	Po	0-4	late 20th to early 21st c.	24	0,04	23	0,04	1	0	0	0	4	0,25	4	0	0	0	0	0
Po 3	Po	4-8	late 20th to early 21st c.	23	0,04	22	0,05	1	0	0	0	9	0,11	2	0	0	0	0	0
Po 3	Po	8-12	late 20th to early 21st c.	37	0	33	0	1	0	3	0	19	0	4	0	0	0	1	0
Po 3	Po	12-16	late 20th to early 21st c.	48	0	38	0	9	0	1	0	21	0	6	0	0	0	5	0
Po 3	Po	16-20	late 20th to early 21st c.	54	0	50	0	4	0	0	0	27	0	6	0	0	0	2	0
Po 3	Po	20-25	late 20th to early 21st c.	61	0	57	0	4	0	0	0	38	0	6	0	1	0	2	0
Po 3	Po	25-30	late 20th to early 21st c.	73	0,03	63	0,03	9	0	1	0	39	0,05	8	0	2	0	5	0
Po 3	Po	30-35	late 20th to early 21st c.	82	0,02	71	0,01	11	0,09	0	0	53	0,02	7	0	2	0,5	7	0
Po 3	Po	35-40	late 20th to early 21st c.	48	0	46	0	2	0	0	0	21	0	7	0	0	0	1	0
Po 3	Po	40-45	late 20th to early 21st c.	74	0,01	62	0,02	11	0	1	0	32	0,03	16	0	1	0	8	0
Po 3	Po	45-50	late 20th to early 21st c.	60	0,03	47	0,02	13	0,08	0	0	29	0,03	11	0	4	0,25	7	0
Po 3	Po	50-55	late 20th to early 21st c.	48	0,08	39	0,08	8	0,13	1	0	28	0,11	4	0	1	1	4	0
Po 3	Po	55-60	late 20th to early 21st c.	43	0,09	33	0,06	9	0,22	1	0	26	0,08	1	0	3	0,67	4	0
Po 3	Po	60-65	late 20th to early 21st c.	63	0,1	49	0,04	14	0,29	0	0	29	0,07	7	0	3	1	4	0
Po 3	Po	65-70	late 20th to early 21st c.	53	0,23	41	0,15	11	0,55	1	0	31	0,19	2	0	5	1	3	0
Po 3	Po	70-75	late 20th to early 21st c.	80	0,14	65	0,15	15	0,07	0	0	53	0,17	3	0	3	0,33	7	0
Po 3	Po	75-80	late 20th to early 21st c.	40	0,2	29	0,24	11	0,09	0	0	17	0,41	2	0	5	0,2	4	0
Po 3	Po	80-85	late 20th to early 21st c.	38	0,05	33	0,06	5	0	0	0	21	0,1	4	0	2	0	3	0
Po 3	Po	85-90	late 20th to early 21st c.	50	0,1	22	0,09	22	0,11	0	0	18	0,17	4	0	15	0,07	4	0,25
Po 3	Po	90-95	late 19th to early 20th c.	33	0,27	25	0,2	8	0,5	0	0	14	0,36	3	0	7	0,57	1	0
Po 3	Po	95-100	late 19th to early 20th c.	80	0,1	51	0,1	29	0,1	0	0	33	0,12	6	0	21	0,14	4	0

Supplementary table 2 continued

Station	Region	Core depth (cm)	Time bin	All mollusks		Bivalves		Gastropods		Scaphopods		<i>Varicorbula gibba</i>		<i>Kurtiella bidentata</i>		<i>Turritellinella tricarinata</i>		<i>Tritia varicosa</i>	
				N	DF	N	DF	N	DF	N	DF	N	DF	N	DF	N	DF	N	DF
Po 3	Po	100-105	late 19th to early 20th c.	40	0,05	32	0,03	8	0,13	0	0	10	0,1	5	0	6	0,17	0	0
Po 3	Po	105-110	late 19th to early 20th c.	38	0,08	26	0,08	12	0,08	0	0	11	0,09	7	0	9	0,11	1	0
Po 3	Po	110-115	late 19th to early 20th c.	38	0,11	30	0,1	8	0,13	0	0	10	0,2	7	0	4	0,25	2	0
Po 3	Po	115-120	late 19th to early 20th c.	29	0,14	18	0,17	11	0,09	0	0	8	0,38	2	0	5	0,2	3	0
Po 3	Po	120-125	late 19th to early 20th c.	28	0,07	15	0	11	0,18	2	0	6	0	2	0	7	0,29	1	0
Po 3	Po	125-130	late 19th to early 20th c.	27	0,15	14	0	13	0,31	0	0	3	0	2	0	12	0,33	1	0
Po 3	Po	130-135	late 19th to early 20th c.	28	0	16	0	12	0	0	0	9	0	2	0	12	0	0	0
Po 3	Po	135-140	late 19th to early 20th c.	24	0,04	17	0,06	7	0	0	0	7	0	3	0,33	7	0	0	0
Po 3	Po	140-145	late 19th to early 20th c.	17	0,12	6	0	11	0,18	0	0	3	0	2	0	11	0,18	0	0
Po 3	Po	145-150	late 19th to early 20th c.	17	0,12	11	0,09	6	0,17	0	0	3	0	3	0,33	5	0,2	0	0
Po 3	Po	150-152	late 19th to early 20th c.	12	0,08	11	0,09	1	0	0	0	2	0	2	0,5	1	0	0	0
Po 4	Po	0-4	late 20th to early 21st c.	43	0	40	0	3	0	0	0	13	0	7	0	2	0	0	0
Po 4	Po	4-8	late 20th to early 21st c.	67	0	56	0	10	0	1	0	31	0	4	0	6	0	2	0
Po 4	Po	8-12	late 20th to early 21st c.	25	0	20	0	5	0	0	0	9	0	0	0	2	0	0	0
Po 4	Po	12-16	late 20th to early 21st c.	32	0	27	0	5	0	0	0	15	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
Po 4	Po	16-20	late 20th to early 21st c.	49	0	41	0	7	0	1	0	18	0	2	0	2	0	0	0
Po 4	Po	20-25	late 20th to early 21st c.	105	0,04	90	0,03	15	0,07	0	0	53	0,06	5	0	4	0,25	5	0
Po 4	Po	25-30	late 20th to early 21st c.	128	0,02	106	0,03	22	0	0	0	59	0,05	7	0	4	0	7	0
Po 4	Po	30-35	late 20th to early 21st c.	96	0,04	84	0,05	12	0	0	0	54	0,06	10	0,1	3	0	3	0
Po 4	Po	35-40	late 20th to early 21st c.	139	0,03	108	0,04	31	0	0	0	58	0,07	39	0	6	0	14	0
Po 4	Po	40-45	late 20th to early 21st c.	88	0	69	0	19	0	0	0	39	0	17	0	6	0	6	0
Po 4	Po	45-50	late 20th to early 21st c.	130	0,03	92	0,04	38	0	0	0	73	0,04	4	0	3	0	15	0
Po 4	Po	50-55	late 20th to early 21st c.	184	0,03	120	0,04	63	0,02	1	0	84	0,05	9	0,11	3	0	32	0,03
Po 4	Po	55-60	late 20th to early 21st c.	56	0,04	32	0	23	0,09	1	0	18	0	1	0	4	0,5	16	0
Po 4	Po	60-65	late 20th to early 21st c.	168	0,11	112	0,08	56	0,16	0	0	75	0,12	11	0	11	0,73	32	0,03
Po 4	Po	65-70	late 20th to early 21st c.	100	0,11	67	0,12	33	0,09	0	0	46	0,17	4	0	6	0,33	15	0
Po 4	Po	70-75	late 20th to early 21st c.	111	0,23	83	0,29	28	0,07	0	0	51	0,45	8	0	10	0,2	12	0
Po 4	Po	75-80	late 20th to early 21st c.	156	0,16	132	0,19	24	0	0	0	82	0,29	16	0	3	0	10	0
Po 4	Po	80-85	late 20th to early 21st c.	98	0,09	78	0,09	20	0,1	0	0	42	0,14	10	0	9	0,22	1	0
Po 4	Po	85-90	late 20th to early 21st c.	54	0,06	37	0,08	17	0	0	0	12	0,25	12	0	9	0	1	0
Po 4	Po	90-95	late 19th to early 20th c.	118	0,02	82	0,02	36	0	0	0	31	0,06	31	0	27	0	2	0
Po 4	Po	95-100	late 19th to early 20th c.	44	0	31	0	12	0	1	0	12	0	9	0	10	0	1	0
Po 4	Po	100-105	late 19th to early 20th c.	76	0,05	55	0,05	19	0,05	2	0	17	0,18	20	0	11	0	1	0
Po 4	Po	105-110	late 19th to early 20th c.	54	0,02	41	0	13	0,08	0	0	17	0	14	0	10	0,1	1	0
Po 4	Po	110-115	late 19th to early 20th c.	52	0,06	32	0,03	20	0,1	0	0	14	0,07	8	0	14	0,14	4	0
Po 4	Po	115-120	late 19th to early 20th c.	57	0,07	34	0,09	21	0,05	2	0	16	0,19	9	0	15	0	3	0
Po 4	Po	120-125	late 19th to early 20th c.	40	0,1	26	0,08	14	0,14	0	0	11	0	9	0	9	0,22	1	0
Po 4	Po	125-130	late 19th to early 20th c.	45	0,09	29	0,03	16	0,19	0	0	10	0	12	0,08	14	0,21	0	0
Po 4	Po	130-135	late 19th to early 20th c.	42	0,02	27	0	15	0,07	0	0	8	0	5	0	11	0,09	1	0
Po 4	Po	135-140	late 19th to early 20th c.	20	0,15	11	0	9	0,33	0	0	4	0	3	0	8	0,38	0	0
Po 4	Po	140-145	late 19th to early 20th c.	28	0,07	19	0,05	9	0,11	0	0	5	0,2	6	0	7	0	0	0
Po 4	Po	145-150	late 19th to early 20th c.	19	0,21	13	0,08	5	0,6	1	0	2	0	2	0	4	0,75	0	0
Po 4	Po	150-155	late 19th to early 20th c.	16	0	10	0	6	0	0	0	4	0	1	0	1	0	5	0
205-S9	Po	2440-2450	middle to late Holocene	24	0,17	19	0,16	5	0,2	0	0	11	0,27	3	0	4	0,25	1	0
205-S9	Po	2578-2583	middle to late Holocene	48	0,19	27	0,15	17	0,29	4	0	13	0,23	4	0	15	0,33	0	0
EM-S7	Po	1950-1956	middle to late Holocene	27	0,22	17	0	10	0,6	0	0	9	0	2	0	8	0,63	1	0
EM-S7	Po	1970-1976	middle to late Holocene	31	0,13	24	0,17	7	0	0	0	14	0,29	1	0	3	0	0	0
EM-S7	Po	1976-1982	middle to late Holocene	99	0,18	70	0,2	24	0,17	5	0	41	0,22	1	0	13	0,31	3	0
205-S9	Po	2250-2255	middle to late Holocene	30	0,2	19	0,32	9	0	2	0	10	0,2	4	0,25	0	0	6	0
205-S9	Po	2274-2280	middle to late Holocene	55	0,13	35	0,11	15	0,2	5	0	19	0,21	7	0	5	0,4	3	0
EM-S13	Po	2255-2260	middle to late Holocene	67	0,13	43	0,12	22	0,18	2	0	22	0,09	8	0,13	8	0,5	5	0
EM-S13	Po	2555-2560	middle to late Holocene	30	0,07	25	0,04	4	0,25	1	0	17	0,06	2	0	0	0	0	0

Supplementary table 3

Total assemblage

	PP	Po3	Po4	Panzano
middle-late Holocene	9	0	0	0
17th to early 19th c.	0	0	0	21
late 19th to early 20th c	0	13	13	6
late 20th to early 21st c.	0	19	19	4

Bivalves

	PP	Po3	Po4	Panzano
middle-late Holocene	6	0	0	0
17th to early 19th c.	0	0	0	21
late 19th to early 20th c	0	5	9	6
late 20th to early 21st c.	0	19	19	4

Gastropods

	PP	Po3	Po4	Panzano
middle-late Holocene	2	0	0	0
17th to early 19th c.	0	0	0	21
late 19th to early 20th c	0	1	3	6
late 20th to early 21st c.	0	1	10	4

Scaphopods

	PP	Po3	Po4	Panzano
middle-late Holocene	0	0	0	0
17th to early 19th c.	0	0	0	0
late 19th to early 20th c	0	0	0	3
late 20th to early 21st c.	0	0	0	1

Varicorbula gibba

	PP	Po3	Po4	Panzano
middle-late Holocene	2	0	0	0
17th to early 19th c.	0	0	0	19
late 19th to early 20th c	0	1	1	6
late 20th to early 21st c.	0	14	13	4

Kurtiella bidentata

	PP	Po3	Po4	Panzano
middle-late Holocene	0	0	0	0
17th to early 19th c.	0	0	0	20
late 19th to early 20th c	0	0	2	6
late 20th to early 21st c.	0	0	1	3

Turritellinella tricarinata

	PP	Po3	Po4	Panzano
middle-late Holocene	0	0	0	0
17th to early 19th c.	0	0	0	17
late 19th to early 20th c	0	1	1	6
late 20th to early 21st c.	0	0	0	1

Tritia varicosa

	PP	Po3	Po4	Panzano
middle-late Holocene	0	0	0	0
17th to early 19th c.	0	0	0	0
late 19th to early 20th c	0	0	0	6
late 20th to early 21st c.	0	0	2	4

Supplementary table 4

	Number of shells		Drilling frequencies		odds.ratio	lcl	ucl	p-value
	Pre-anthropogenic	Post-anthropogenic	Pre-anthropogenic	Post-anthropogenic				
<i>Varicorbula gibba</i>	1689	1749	0,2931	0,1515	2,321	1,9574	2,7561	< 0,0001
<i>Turritellinella tricarinata</i>	1354	204	0,483	0,3186	1,9971	1,4473	2,7778	< 0,0001
<i>Kurtiella bidentata</i>	1896	448	0,3513	0,2321	1,7906	1,4041	2,297	< 0,0001
<i>Tritia varicata</i>	442	556	0,0679	0,0432	1,6133	0,8965	2,9314	0,0923